

Universidad de
Castilla-La Mancha

IV Jornadas Científicas de Estudiantes de la SEB

(Sociedad Española de Biometría)

Albacete, 5 y 6 de septiembre de 2019

Agrupación Politécnica de Albacete
(Edificio Infante Don Juan Manuel)

**Poster session
September 5th, 18:15 to 19:15**

Design of an alternative delimiting strategy for the *Xylella fastidiosa* infection in Alicante: a development of a sequential adaptive algorithm for optimising survey and sampling.

E. Lázaro¹, M. Sesé², A. López-Quílez², D. Conesa², A. Ferrer³, V. Dalmau³ and A. Vicent¹

¹Centre de Protecció Vegetal i Biotecnologia, Institut Valencià d'Investigacions Agràries, Moncada

²Departament d'Estadística e Investigació Operativa, Universitat de València, Burjassot

³Servei de Sanitat Vegetal, Conselleria d'Agricultura, Medi Ambient, Canvi Climàtic i Desenvolupament Rural, Silla

Xylella fastidiosa (*Xf*) is a regulated quarantine plant pathogen in the European Union (EU). The current legal provisions specify the implementation of delimiting surveys in infested areas to demarcate the geographic extent and implement eradication or containment measures (EU, 2015). North-eastern Alicante Province, Spain, is one of the areas infested by *Xf* in the EU, and so it is currently demarcated and subjected to a delimiting survey activity. Based on the 2018 official surveillance program, in which approximately 100,000 has. were surveyed and 11,000 samples were taken and analysed, this work aimed to improve the efficiency of the current delimiting survey strategy.

A generic delimiting strategy was designed based on a three-phase adaptive approach in which the surveyed area (epidemiological unit) size and sampling intensity were tailored according to the previous phase information (Peyrard et al., 2013). An algorithm was implemented to optimise the number of epidemiological units to be surveyed and the sample size by simulating different random sampling scenarios from the reference data. Strategy evaluation was performed by comparing the delimitation efficacy and incidence estimates between the proposed and the current strategy. Incidence was modelled by means of a Bayesian spatial hierarchical model in which climatic and spatial factors were evaluated using INLA approximation (Lindgren and Rue, 2015). The proposed delimiting strategies achieved to delimit similar extension disease (similar efficacy) with a lower number of samples (better efficiency) than current.

Keywords: spatial sampling, adaptive sampling, simulations-optimization.

References

EU (2015). Commission implementing decision (EU) 2015/789 of 18 May 2015 as regards measures to prevent the introduction into and the spread within the union of *Xylella fastidiosa*. *Official Journal of the European Union*, L125: 3653.